

1 Natural noise management in collaborative
2 recommender systems over time-related information

3 Francisco J. Baldán^a, Raciél Yera^{a,*}, Luis Martínez^a

4 ^a*Computer Science Department, University of Jaén, Jaén, Spain*

5 **Abstract**

Recommender systems are currently a suitable alternative for providing easy and appropriate access to information for users in today's digital information-overloaded world. However, an important drawback of these systems is the inconsistent behavior of users in providing item preferences. To address this issue, several natural noise management (NNM) approaches have been proposed, which positively influence recommendation accuracy. However, a major limitation of such previous works is *the disregarding of the time-related information* coupled to the rating data in RSs. Based on this motivation, this paper proposes two novel methods, named SeqNNM and SeqNNM-p for NNM focused on an incremental, time-aware recommender system scenario that has not yet been considered, by performing a classification-based NNM over specific preference sequences, driven by their associated timestamps. Such methods have been evaluated by simulating a real-time scenario and using metrics such as Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Root-Mean-Square error (RMSE), Precision, Recall, NDCG, number of modified ratings, and running time. The obtained experimental results show that in the used settings, it is possible to achieve better recommendation accuracy with a low intrusion degree. Furthermore, the main innovation associated with the overall contribution is the screening of natural noise management approaches to be used on specific preferences subsets, and not

*Corresponding author
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(f.baldan@ujaen.es (Francisco J. Baldán), ryera@ujaen.es (Raciél Yera), martin@ujaen.es (Luis Martínez))

over the whole dataset as discussed by previous authors. These proposed approaches allow the use of natural noise management in large datasets, in which it would be very difficult to correct the entire data.

6 *Keywords:* Time-aware noise correction, Natural noise management,
7 user inconsistencies, collaborative filtering, recommender systems

8 **1. Introduction**

9 Recommender systems (RS) currently represent an appropriate solution for
10 the problem associated with efficient information access in today's digital world
11 (Adomavicius & Tuzhilin, 2005; Konstan & Riedl, 2012; Jannach et al., 2021;
12 Yera et al., 2023). Specifically, collaborative filtering (CF) has been highlighted
13 as a very appropriate paradigm to implement these systems because they are
14 able to produce accurate recommendations requiring a minimum amount of
15 information (Ekstrand et al., 2011).

16 User-user collaborative filtering, as a pioneer recommendation approach, was
17 initially introduced by (Resnick et al., 1994) as a way to predict the user's
18 preferences by using the information associated with similar peers associated
19 with a community of people. Later, (Sarwar et al., 2001) extended the idea
20 behind user similarity and defined item-item CF algorithms that are based on
21 item-based similarities and outperform user-user methods in terms of accuracy
22 and scalability (Deshpande & Karypis, 2004). (Koren et al., 2009) popularized a
23 new paradigm for CF, proposing dimensionality reduction methods that notably
24 improve the performance of traditional methods. In addition, a lot of notable
25 research has been developed in order to do a deeper exploration of user ratings
26 to enhance the recommendation process (Bobadilla et al., 2013; De Pessemier
27 et al., 2014; Wei et al., 2017; Yera & Martínez, 2017; Yu et al., 2017; Wang &
28 Mishra, 2017; Van Dat et al., 2022; Yannam et al., 2023).

29 In this way, although the focus on recommender systems research began in
30 the 90s (Resnick & Varian, 1997), it has been evolving across the time in a very
31 active and prolific research field in which currently there are several hot topics
32 such as the item recommendation from implicit feedback (Rendle, 2022), the
33 use of deep learning (Zhang et al., 2022), the context-aware recommendation
34 (Adomavicius et al., 2022), the group recommendation (Masthoff & Delić, 2022),
35 the cross-domain recommendation (Dacrema et al., 2022), and the explainability
36 (Tintarev & Masthoff, 2022), among other popular research efforts.

37 On the other hand, the preprocessing process of inconsistent user
38 preferences in RS has also become an emerging field of study, mainly focused
39 on movie recommendations (Pham & Jung, 2013; Yera et al., 2015; Luo et al.,
40 2023). Several authors have stated that user ratings in recommender systems
41 are intrinsically inconsistent because of imperfect and even unintentional user
42 behaviors while they express their preferences, limiting their performance with
43 a *magic barrier* (Said et al., 2012).

44 Extant research has provided different examples of the presence of natural
45 noise in recommender systems:

- 46 • (Amatriain et al., 2009) have suggested that preference values should not
47 be regarded as ground-truth values because the rating gathering is a noisy
48 process.
- 49 • (Pham & Jung, 2013) pointed out two probable causes for the presence
50 of natural noise in recommender systems datasets, which are: 1) the fact
51 that user preferences change across time, and 2) the users are imprecise
52 when they provide rating values.
- 53 • (Said et al., 2012) and (Kluver et al., 2012) have indicated that users'
54 imprecision can be caused by personal conditions, social influences,
55 emotional states, or certain rating scales.

- 56 • (Yera et al., 2015) have presented an illustrative example of natural noise,
57 where a low rating is considered noisy if the corresponding user usually
58 evaluates positively most of the items, and the associated item has been
59 voted high by the majority of the items.
- 60 • (Yera et al., 2019) also presents an illustrative example of natural noise,
61 where the noise degree of a rating is characterized by the number and
62 weights of the identified user’s behaviors/regularities that the rating
63 contradicts or does not verify. In this way, it is identified as noisy, a
64 rating that causes the user to not follow a pattern/regularity with high
65 support.

66 To overcome these issues, some works have been proposed in the last few
67 years, focusing on detecting, removing, or correcting naturally noisy ratings
68 by using their own rating information or information obtained from external
69 sources (O’Mahony et al., 2006; Pham & Jung, 2013; Yera et al., 2015; Castro
70 et al., 2017; Zhu et al., 2018; Luo et al., 2023). In addition, there have been
71 studies centered on detecting whole noisy-but-non-malicious user profiles (Li
72 et al., 2013).

73 Previous research has focused on traditional evaluation setups that use
74 ratings to create training and test sets and employ them to evaluate the
75 accuracy of the corresponding method; in this scenario, these methods imply
76 an improvement in the recommendation performance (Gunawardana & Shani,
77 2009). However, the data associated with a real-time recommender system do
78 not match these settings. In the real-world scenario, preferences are
79 incrementally entered, and therefore, rating sorting begins to play a relevant
80 role here (Alabduljabbar et al., 2023; Chen et al., 2021a; Tran & Huh, 2023).
81 Furthermore, the system must simultaneously capture this temporal
82 information and provide user rating predictions. Then, the addition of natural

83 noise management into this new scenario requires a solution to several
84 limitations that are connected with the application of the noise correction
85 approach in RS datasets. Some of these limitations are: 1) to explore whether
86 the application of natural noise management in some segment of recent data
87 instead of the whole dataset would be effective in improving accuracy; 2) to
88 explore the magnitude of the associated improvement degree; 3) to identify
89 how this accuracy could vary across different lengths of the rating sequences;
90 and 4) to evaluate other important criteria in natural noise management, such
91 as the intrusion level and the running time, for performing a trade-off with the
92 accuracy, and therefore suggest conclusions in order to use the new approaches
93 in real scenarios. This paper focuses on supporting these issues by exploring
94 approaches for performing natural noise management in such time-related
95 recommendation scenarios.

96 Specifically, the main novel contributions of this paper in relation to previous
97 proposals and existing similar approaches are:

- 98 • The screening of the natural noise management process, tailored to an
99 incremental, time-aware recommendation scenario.
- 100 • The development of a comparison protocol between the time-aware natural
101 noise management and the traditional natural noise management approach
102 without the time dimension.
- 103 • An extensive evaluation of the time-aware natural noise management
104 performance, using as new rating predictors in a natural noise management
105 context, up to ten different state-of-the-art recommendation approaches. It
106 includes 1) a clustering-based method (George & Merugu, 2005), 2) a basic
107 neighborhood-based method (Resnick et al., 1994), 3) a neighborhood-
108 based method including average deviation (Resnick et al., 1994), 4) a
109 neighborhood-based

110 method that includes biased-based baselines modeling (Resnick et al.,
111 1994), 5) a method based on negative matrix factorization (Luo et al.,
112 2013), 6) the Koren’s basic SVD approach (Koren et al., 2009), 7) the
113 Koren’s SVD approach with temporal information (Koren, 2010), 8) the
114 slope-one approach (Lemire & Maclachlan, 2005), 9) a baseline only
115 approach predicting the biased-based baseline estimate for given user
116 and item (Koren, 2010), and 10) a normal predictor based on the
117 distribution of the training set, highlighted by (Hug, 2020).

- 118 • The overall evidence is that a natural noise management approach that
119 incorporates time-related information and time windows is able to reduce
120 the method’s intrusiveness, decrease the execution time, as well as lead to
121 a similar or improved accuracy.

122 The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents previous studies
123 related to recommender systems and natural noise management in
124 collaborative recommendations and justifies the selection of a specific
125 approach to be used as the base for the following sections. Section 3 describes
126 new approaches for performing the natural noise management task in an
127 incremental, time-aware movie recommendation scenario. Section 4 plans and
128 develops an experimental framework to evaluate the new NNM framework
129 tailored to the time-related context. Finally, we present a final discussion
130 about the obtained results. Section 5 concludes the paper.

131 2. Preliminaries

132 In this section, we present the necessary background for easy following and
133 understanding of our proposal. It includes some antecedents for movie
134 recommender systems, for previous works about the management of natural
135 noise or unintentional inconsistencies that users can introduce in RS, as well as

136 a detailed reference to a pioneer work on natural noise management that will
137 be used as the basis for the current proposal.

138 *2.1. Antecedents on basic recommender systems*

139 The movie recommendation domain boosted initially the development of
140 modern recommender systems in the middle of the 90s (Resnick et al., 1994;
141 Adomavicius & Tuzhilin, 2005). Two main recommendation paradigms have
142 been modeled over the last 30 years for developing recommendation tools:

143 • **Content-based recommendation:** The basis of content-based
144 recommendation is the use of movie attributes for composing the user
145 and item profiles, considering the relationship between item attributes
146 and the rating values provided by the users (Adomavicius & Tuzhilin,
147 2005). Then, several scoring approaches are employed to recommend the
148 most appropriate movie profiles to each individual user. Some common
149 movie attributes include genre, director, actors, country, year, or each
150 movie’s associated tags (De Gemmis et al., 2015; Pérez-Almaguer et al.,
151 2021; Yera et al., 2022b).

152 In the last few years, several sophisticated approaches have been developed
153 for building the aforementioned user and item profiles. It includes the use
154 of advanced machine learning algorithms, as well as the use of semantic
155 tools such as ontologies (Lops et al., 2019; Van Dat et al., 2022).

156 • **Collaborative filtering-based recommendation:** In the case of
157 collaborative filtering, the working principle relies on crowd preferences
158 to suggest movies for the active user. Specifically, it is based on the
159 discovery, in an explicit or implicit way, of users’ rating patterns that are
160 similar to those associated with the current user and uses their
161 associated information for the recommendation generation (Ning et al.,

162 2015). Two large families of collaborative filtering approaches can be
163 identified: 1) memory-based (Ning et al., 2015), focused on directly
164 finding appropriate users' neighborhoods for the current user and using
165 the preferences of such nearest neighbors for recommendation
166 generation, and 2) model-based (Koren et al., 2009), focused on building
167 intermediate models that comprise the preferences of the user's crowd
168 and can facilitate recommendation generation.

169 Collaborative filtering approaches have been very popular in movie
170 recommendation because they can provide accurate recommendations
171 using only ratings and without any additional information, in contrast to
172 content-based approaches that depend on item attributes for an
173 appropriate performance (Pilászy & Tikk, 2009).

174 Across these traditional approaches, in the last few years, movie
175 recommendations have continuously been a relevant research topic. In this
176 way, (Deldjoo et al., 2019) model a new concept, titled Movie Genome, as a
177 way of alleviating the new item cold start problem in movie recommendation
178 and therefore improving the recommendation accuracy. (Kumar et al., 2020)
179 introduces a movie recommender system using sentiment analysis from
180 microblogging data, leveraging, in this way, the content-based recommendation
181 paradigm. (Widiyaningtyas et al., 2021) explore advanced correlation-based
182 similarities between the user profiles for introducing new algorithms for movie
183 recommendation focused on outperforming previous proposals. In a different
184 direction, (Chen et al., 2021b) exploits users' positive and negative profiles and
185 relies on preferences over movies to compose a novel movie recommendation
186 method.

187 Overall, while most of the available approaches in movie recommendation
188 focus on improving recommendations through the proposal of more

189 sophisticated recommendation algorithms (Goyani & Chaurasiya, 2020), the
190 current paper follows an alternative research path. Specifically, it will focus on
191 the improvement of recommendation accuracy supported by the management
192 of natural noise (Yera et al., 2015; Martínez et al., 2016; Yera et al., 2019)
193 associated with user preferences and the use of time-related information.

194 The next subsection focuses briefly on the incorporation of time-related
195 information into recommender systems.

196 *2.2. Antecedent of time-related information in recommender systems*

197 The value of time-related information in recommender systems was early
198 pointed out by (Ding & Li, 2005), when they presented several weighting
199 approaches to the basic memory-based collaborative filtering scenario, being
200 used the time where the user’s opinion is provided as input for the weights’
201 calculation.

202 More recently, (Campos et al., 2014) presents a large-scale survey on the
203 use of time-aware recommender systems, illustrating a taxonomy for
204 classifying the developed works on the use of time as a contextual dimension
205 in this scenario. They cover three main work categories: 1) continuous
206 time-aware heuristic approaches, 2) categorical time-aware heuristic
207 approaches, and 3) time-adaptive models.

208 (Vinagre et al., 2015) have also developed a survey in a similar direction,
209 identifying several groups of research trends related to different challenges in
210 the field, such as the following:

- 211 • **Time-aware algorithms focused on modeling time as context.** It
212 includes time-aware factorization and time-aware neighborhood models. In
213 the context-aware framework, time features (day, day of the week,
214 working/nonworking hours) were used in the prefiltering, postfiltering, and
215 modeling stages. The main limitation of this approach is related to

216 the way in which the time variable is considered. It is only taken into
217 account as one more variable of the problem, so traditional models are still
218 applied. This modeling makes it especially complex to notice time series
219 behavior of interest, such as concept drift(Rabiu et al., 2020a), which can
220 affect attributes such as user preferences, product popularity, or product
221 characteristics, among others.

- 222 • **Time-dependent algorithms focused on using time as a sequence.**

223 This includes models that attempt to capture the phenomena related to
224 modeling sequential temporal dynamics in recommender systems.

225 Therefore, it deals with issues such as changes and fluctuations in user
226 preferences and item popularity. Here (Vinagre et al., 2015) also considered
227 time-dependent neighborhood models (usually implemented through time
228 decay function or sliding window algorithms) and time-dependent
229 factorization models. One of the potential pitfalls of this approach is the
230 increased complexity of the proposed models compared to traditional
231 models (Jin et al., 2018). Such complexity leads to a significant increase in
232 running time that is related to the temporal/sequential nature of the
233 proposed processing.

234 Eventually, (Vinagre et al., 2015) also point out the separate modeling of
235 short-term and long-term preferences (Ricci et al., 2003), or the bringing to this
236 context of algorithms formerly focused on processing high-speed data streams
237 (Li et al., 2007).

238 More recently, (Rabiu et al., 2020b) presented an updated survey of
239 temporal (time-related) models in recommender systems built on the same
240 framework of (Vinagre et al., 2015). Here, the authors suggest the necessity of
241 incorporating change point detection methods across user preferences to
242 improve the exploitation of the temporal dimension, adding time-related deep

243 learning-based methods in this context, and working toward a tailored
244 evaluation strategy for this scenario.

245 In the last few years, the research line around time-related
246 recommendations has been linked with the topic of sequential
247 recommendation. (Quadrana et al., 2018) formalizes the input of the
248 sequence-aware recommendation problem as an ordered and often
249 timestamped list of past user actions. Furthermore, recently several authors
250 have also introduced several machine learning-related approaches to this
251 research framework, such as contrastive learning (Chen et al., 2022),
252 self-attentive neural architectures (Zhou et al., 2020), or knowledge-graphs
253 (Huang et al., 2019).

254 In summary, the brief research literature presented in this section suggests
255 that the use of time-related information has been a research goal of the
256 research community. However, it is also important to point out that most of
257 the developed approaches are centered on proposing algorithms directly
258 focused on improving the recommendation performance. It is relevant that
259 there is a lack of work systematically focused on the use of time-related
260 information in RS tasks such as the data preprocessing (Amatriain et al.,
261 2010) or the natural noise management (Martínez et al., 2016), according to
262 recent reviews in this field, already referred (Vinagre et al., 2015; Quadrana
263 et al., 2018). This study aims to fill this gap by proposing a time-related
264 natural noise management framework for a movie recommendation scenario.

265 The next section provides an overview of natural noise management
266 approaches in RS, which is necessary for the introduction of the methods
267 presented in this paper.

268 *2.3. Related works on natural noise management in RS*

269 The preprocessing of inconsistent user preferences, so-called natural noise,
270 is a relatively new research field in CFRS. In this case, we referred to the
271 inconsistencies unintentionally introduced by users due to factors like the
272 change of taste over time, personal conditions, inconsistent rating strategies,
273 or social influences, which, therefore, cause the appearance of a “magic
274 barrier” that affects performance (Said et al., 2012); and excluded those
275 inconsistencies deliberately inserted by some users to bias the behavior of the
276 system (Mobasher et al., 2007; Gunes et al., 2014). This second kind of
277 inconsistency, also known as malicious noise, is out of the scope of this paper.

278 The related literature has identified several examples of the consequences
279 of natural noise on the user experience and the system’s performance. Being
280 rating gathering a noisy process (Amatriain et al., 2009), it is possible that a
281 user could provide a 5-star noisy rating to some item that does not deserve
282 due to lack of attention implying the subsequent, erroneous recommendation,
283 of items linked to the rated one. Furthermore, the current preference over some
284 items, e.g. movies, could be conditioned by issues such as the release date, the
285 advertising associated with the actors, directors, or the movie itself (Pham &
286 Jung, 2013). Therefore, items preferred by some users in the past could not be
287 preferred at present; conversely, some items disliked in the past could be loved
288 now. Additionally, information from social networks could temporally condition
289 the values of the ratings provided by the user (Said et al., 2012). For example,
290 a 5-star item could be voted with two stars if the user reads negative comments
291 about this item. In a different direction, the variation across diverse rating
292 scales in preference gathering systems, such as $[0, 5]$ or $[0, 10]$, creates confusion
293 in the users and then leads to the introduction of natural noise.

294 The presence of noisy ratings that contradict the common behaviors or

295 regularities of the users (Yera et al., 2019), would then imply a negative
296 impact on the recommendation accuracy, taking into account that most of the
297 recommendation approaches are built over the identification of common users’
298 behaviors.

299 (O’Mahony et al., 2006) introduced the first study that uses the term
300 “natural noise”. Here, the authors focus on identifying whether a rating is
301 noise-free or contains natural noise. For this purpose, they determine the
302 consistency between the original rating value and a new value predicted
303 through a recommendation algorithm for the same user-item pair. (Amatriain
304 et al., 2009) also considers that the characterization of natural noise is a key
305 element in the RS research field. Initially, they analyze the response provided
306 by traditional recommendation methods in natural noise conditions using data
307 obtained in three different moments: the second one 24 hours after the first
308 one, and the third one at least 15 days after the third one. This analysis shows
309 that the error prediction considerably varies for each case. Then, the core of
310 the work proposes a user-dependent procedure to remove these inconsistencies
311 by assuming that there are several available ratings associated with the same
312 user about the same item (one rating and several re-ratings). (Pham & Jung,
313 2013) have proposed a preference-based approach for rating correction in RS.
314 This proposal focuses on the use of item attributes to represent user
315 preferences and the detection and correction of ratings that do not match the
316 corresponding user preference models. Eventually, (Li et al., 2013) also
317 presented a method for the inconsistencies handling in CF datasets. In this
318 case, their method works at the user level, detecting noisy but non-malicious
319 users whose preferences can affect the recommendation accuracy. Specifically,
320 the proposal assumes that the ratings provided by the same user on closely
321 correlated items should have similar scores. Then, it captures and accumulates

322 the user’s contradictions and uses them to remove the top noisy profiles. This
323 removal implies an improvement in the recommendation’s accuracy.

324 More recently, keeping in mind the same goal, the degree of user coherence
325 in RS datasets has been measured using item attributes (e.g., directors,
326 actors), showing that the recommendation accuracy is improved when the
327 users with a lower coherence are discarded (Bellogín et al., 2014). This work is
328 continued by (Yu et al., 2016), proposing a correction approach for the
329 preferences associated with such low-coherence users. In parallel, (Saia et al.,
330 2016) presented an approach that uses semantic information to remove
331 incoherent items from user profiles in recommendation scenarios. On the other
332 hand, (Yera et al., 2015) and (Castro et al., 2017) proposed a natural noise
333 management method for collaborative RS based on a correction paradigm. In
334 contrast to previous studies, it does not depend on additional information
335 beyond the rating matrix, like item attributes or user feedback. In this case,
336 the method uses a previous classification approach to characterize user and
337 item behavior and detects anomalous ratings based on this classification.
338 Finally, for these tagged ratings, a correction process is performed by
339 calculating a new rating value for the same user-item pair using the remaining
340 ratings and a traditional CF technique. In particular, corrections are made if
341 the difference between the old and new ratings is higher than the threshold. In
342 this case, the predictor used to calculate such ratings was Resnick’s user-based
343 CF method with Pearson’s similarity (UserKNNPearson) (Resnick et al.,
344 1994).

345 Over the last few years, several authors have extended the pioneering work
346 developed by (Yera et al., 2015), being enriched with further computational
347 intelligence techniques and extending the initial ideas. In this way, (Zhu et al.,
348 2018) takes advantage of the correlations between the entropy of the rating

349 data and the prediction uncertainty in terms of evaluation metrics and
350 develops a new denoising algorithm based on fuzzy clustering. The authors
351 assume that the recommendation accuracy is specific to natural noise and that
352 the entropy of an individual rating dataset indicates the uncertainty derived
353 from noisy data. Furthermore, the fuzzy C-means algorithm is used for noisy
354 rating verification. Recently, (Luo et al., 2023) presented a new approach for
355 natural noise management in recommender systems that detects natural noise
356 according to the inconsistency between rating behaviors and users' and items'
357 categories in a similar way to (Yera et al., 2015). Furthermore, the authors
358 consider the probability that each user belongs to each subcategory and
359 correct the natural noise with threshold values weighted by probabilities.

360 In parallel, (Wang et al., 2021) follows the same scheme and proposes an
361 approach that employs fuzzy theory to handle natural noise in RS by
362 classifying ratings into three fuzzy categories characterized by variable
363 boundaries. Subsequently, fuzzy profiles of users and items are constructed to
364 effectively identify natural noise within the ratings. Upon detecting noisy
365 ratings, the authors employ the Maximum Membership Principle to replace
366 them with rating threshold values. Also, (Bag et al., 2019) re-classifies users
367 and items of a system into three classes, namely strong, average, and weak, to
368 identify and correct noise ratings. Subsequently, this study integrates the
369 Bhattacharya coefficient, a well-performing similarity measure for a sparse
370 dataset, with the proposed reclassification method to predict unrated items
371 from the obtained noise-free sparse dataset and recommend preferred products
372 to consumers. In addition, deep learning-based architectures have also been
373 used for natural noise management in RS. Recently, (Park et al., 2023)
374 proposed an autoencoder-based recommender system for exploiting the ability
375 of both anomaly detection and CF. The proposed system detects natural noise

376 in the rating data based on reconstruction errors after training. By removing
377 the detected natural noise, the collaborative filtering approach can predict the
378 unrated ratings using noise-free data.

379 Table 1 summarizes the described methods in terms of four main features:

- 380 • Avoid loss of information: It refers to the fact of avoiding the removal of
381 user preferences across the natural noise management approach.
- 382 • Does not use additional information: It refers to the performance of the
383 noise management without the dependency on information beyond the
384 user preference values. Examples of this additional information could be
385 item attributes or tags.
- 386 • Considers a time-related context: It refers to the use of rating timestamps
387 or similar time-related variables in the developed models.
- 388 • Tailored to a group scenario: It refers to natural noise management models
389 specifically conceived or evaluated in group recommendation scenarios.

390 Works like (O’Mahony et al., 2006) and (Li et al., 2013), even though they
391 do not depend on additional information beyond the rating values, remove
392 important information from the dataset. Other research like the developed by
393 (Pham & Jung, 2013), (Amatriain et al., 2009), (Bellogín et al., 2014), (Yu
394 et al., 2016), and (Saia et al., 2016), although focusing on rating correction
395 and therefore does not imply information loss, also depend on additional
396 information beyond the rating matrix and therefore could be difficult to apply
397 in some scenarios. Eventually, (Yera et al., 2019) introduces a regularity-based
398 correction approach that does not depend on additional information but
399 requires the discovery of intermediate knowledge in terms of association rules,
400 which could be difficult to generalize in some scenarios.

Approach	Avoid loss of information	Does not use additional information	Considers a time-related context	Tailored to a group scenario
(O’Mahony et al., 2006)	-	✓	-	-
(Amatriain et al., 2009)	✓	-	-	-
(Pham & Jung, 2013)	✓	-	-	-
(Li et al., 2013)	-	✓	-	-
(Bellogín et al., 2014)	✓	-	-	-
(Yera et al., 2015)	✓	✓	-	-
(Yu et al., 2016)	✓	-	-	-
(Saia et al., 2016)	✓	-	-	-
(Castro et al., 2017)	✓	✓	-	✓
(Zhu et al., 2018)	✓	✓	-	-
(Bag et al., 2019)	✓	✓	-	-
(Yera et al., 2019)	✓	✓	-	-
(Wang et al., 2021)	✓	✓	-	-
(Luo et al., 2023)	✓	✓	-	-
(Park et al., 2023)	-	✓	-	-
This work	✓	✓	✓	-

Table 1: Comparative analysis of existing approaches.

401 In contrast to the abovementioned works, the previous classification-based
402 approach developed by (Yera et al., 2015) and (Castro et al., 2017), also
403 featured recently by (Bag et al., 2019) and (Luo et al., 2023), correct ratings,
404 does not remove important information from the dataset, and does not depend
405 on additional information such as item attributes. In this way, while most of
406 the considered approaches are centered on individual recommendation, (Castro
407 et al., 2017) have introduced natural noise management in group recommender
408 systems.

409 Therefore, considering the advantages of the previous classification-based
410 approach for natural noise management (Yera et al., 2015), as well as its
411 increasing popularity according to recent works that have continued this
412 approach (Bag et al., 2019; Luo et al., 2023), see Table 1, the rest of the paper
413 will take the pioneering previous classification-based approach (Yera et al.,
414 2015), as the base for the current proposal. As presented in Table 1, the

415 current proposal provides a novel feature in managing a time-related context,
416 which contrasts previous approaches that do not consider it. We leave to
417 future work the tailoring to a group recommendation scenario.

418 *2.4. The classification-based approach for natural noise management in RS*

419 The classification-based approach for natural noise management in RS
420 (Figure 1) was proposed as a way to perform this task without using
421 additional information beyond the user ratings (Yera et al., 2015).

422 This approach comprises two main stages: 1) the detection of possible noisy
423 ratings, and 2) the correction of noisy ratings.

424 The first stage performs a classification of users and items based on a
425 direct inspection of their ratings, to identify tendencies to have low, medium,
426 or high preferences. Overall, the ratings that do not match those
427 well-identified tendencies are considered as possible noisy. This is the
428 underlying technique behind this stage.

429 Specifically, each user, item, and rating are respectively classified into three
430 possible classes, which are presented in Table 2. Specifically, it focuses on
431 classifying users in the classes benevolent, average, critical, or variable; and
432 items in the classes strongly-preferred, averagely-preferred, weakly-preferred,
433 or variably-preferred. Variable and variably-preferred classes are used
434 respectively for users and items that can not be classified into specific classes.
435 Besides, ratings can be classified as weak, average, or strong, depending on two
436 thresholds. Algorithm A.1 (included in Appendix A) shows the pseudocode of
437 this process also included in our new proposals. Moreover, the proposal
438 considers three groups that establish matching among user, item, and rating
439 classes. The proposed method assumes that for a certain rating, if its user and
440 item classes belong to the same group (different from the variable class), then
441 the rating should belong to the corresponding rating class in the same group.

442 Otherwise, the rating should be classified as a possible inconsistency.

Figure 1: Global scheme of the previous classification-based approach for natural noise management.

Table 2: Group of homologous classes

	User class	Item class	Rating class
Group 1	Critical	Weakly-preferred	Weak
Group 2	Average	Averagely-preferred	Average
Group 3	Benevolent	Strongly-preferred	Strong

443 Table 3 presents criteria for classifying users and items using such rating
 444 classification. In the case of users, it assumes that for each user u the sets
 445 $|W_u|$, $|A_u|$ and $|S_u|$ are the respective sets of weak, average, and strong ratings.
 446 Regarding the proportion of ratings in each class, the user is classified as critical,
 447 benevolent, or average, and those users who have a similar proportion of the
 448 three kinds of ratings are classified as variable users. In the case of items, it
 449 follows a very similar approach in relation to users but considers all the ratings
 450 associated with the item (see also Table 3). Here, sets $|W_i|$, $|A_i|$, and $|S_i|$
 451 are used as the respective weakly-preferred, averagely-preferred, and strongly-
 452 preferred ratings for item i .

Table 3: Classes definition

User classes	Definition
Critical	$ W_u > A_u + S_u $
Average	$ A_u > W_u + S_u $
Benevolent	$ S_u > W_u + A_u $
Item classes	Definition
Weakly-preferred	$ W_i > A_i + S_i $
Averagely-preferred	$ A_i > W_i + S_i $
Strongly-preferred	$ S_i > W_i + A_i $

453 The second stage of the proposal is focused on correcting the ratings
454 identified as possible inconsistencies, obtained in the previous stage.
455 Specifically, a new rating value is predicted for each user-item pair associated
456 with the possible noisy rating previously detected. This stage then uses an
457 underlying rating prediction algorithm, which is the well-known Resnick’s
458 user-based method with Pearson’s similarity (UserKNNPearson) (Resnick
459 et al., 1994), as the former collaborative filtering approach. In each case, if the
460 original rating is sufficiently different from the predicted value, the old rating
461 is replaced with the new one. In the proposal, the difference threshold was set
462 to $\delta = 1$, as this value tends to be the minimum step between two ratings in
463 recommendation scenarios. Algorithm A.2 (included in Appendix A) presents
464 this procedure, which is included in our new proposals.

465 As presented in this section, several authors have pointed out that user
466 preferences evolve over time and that taking this issue into account leads to
467 performance improvement in RS models (Vinagre et al., 2015; Huang et al., 2019;
468 Chen et al., 2022). It is then necessary to explore how the use of time-related
469 information affects the behavior of this natural noise management model, which
470 has already been justified. Therefore, two new proposals for performing natural
471 noise management in an incremental, time-related recommendation scenario are
472 presented in the next section.

473 **3. Correcting noisy ratings in a time-aware recommendation scenario**

474 The recommendation tasks are intrinsically incremental, taking into account
475 that the ratings stored behind a CF recommender system are provided by users
476 who simultaneously request suggestions from the system itself. However, as
477 presented in the Introduction section, the use of natural noise management
478 approaches to this incremental scenario brings new issues that have not yet been
479 regarded, and to the best of our knowledge, no previous studies have focused
480 on solving this task. Typical natural noise management methods receive as
481 input a set of ratings and optionally additional information about them and
482 return as output the corrected set. Under these circumstances, its deployment
483 in an incremental, time-aware scenario faces troubles like the selection of the
484 ratings set to be corrected across time and the selection of the data that must
485 be considered for the correction process. Taking into account the relevancy of
486 the time dimension and sequential recommendation context as research trends,
487 it is necessary to tailor formerly developed natural noise management models to
488 these new requirements and scenarios. Therefore, the goal of the current study is
489 to screen new models for the natural noise management process contextualized
490 to an incremental, time-related recommendation scenario.

491 These models use as underlying algorithms the approach for identifying
492 possibly noisy ratings, and the approach for correcting noisy ratings. Both
493 algorithms, formerly proposed by Yera et al. (2015), have been discussed in
494 Section 2.4 and detailed in Algorithms A.1 and A.2

495 Furthermore, this work developed a comprehensive experimental procedure
496 over several recommendation approaches, with a higher, more general
497 magnitude in relation to the previously referred works on natural noise
498 management. Specifically, the current research work will then screen two
499 frameworks for natural noise management in recommender systems, where it is

500 assumed a sequential gathering of the rating data, which is the real context of
501 a deployed recommender system. The next sections describe these approaches.

502 *3.1. Sequential natural noise management in collaborative filtering*

503 In the first stage, we propose a framework, named SeqNNM, that considers
504 the continuous gathering of sequential rating data by RS. Figure 2 illustrates this
505 framework. Herein, it is assumed that a set of rating sequences $s_1, s_2, \dots, s_k, \dots, s_n$
506 is continuously gathered by the system. Each newly gathered s_k is first added
507 to the main RS dataset R . Then, the $R + s_k$ dataset is corrected through the
508 mentioned natural noise management approach. From the identification of noisy
509 ratings, following Algorithm A.1, and the subsequent prediction of corrected
510 ratings, following the guidelines in Algorithm A.2, a processed dataset is finally
511 obtained with the noise corrected based on the available data up to that moment.
512 The sequential processing of data in specific time steps is the main innovation
513 of this proposal. After that, the data reached as output by the NNM approach
514 started to be used as the main data of the recommender system for both the
515 main recommendation generation process and for the subsequent runs of the
516 NNM process. This procedure processes multiple times all the available data,
517 so it is able to correct a large amount of noise through further intrusion into
518 the original data. Algorithm 1 presents an overview of this framework.

519 *3.2. Sequential natural noise management in collaborative filtering covering the* 520 *last p rating sequences*

521 The framework for sequential natural noise management presented in the
522 previous subsection has a shortcoming of the high volume of data that is used
523 for natural noise management across the processing of each new sequence, which
524 could affect the time performance of the proposal. To alleviate this drawback,
525 we propose an alternative approach, named SeqNNM-p, in which instead of

Figure 2: Overview for the approach for natural noise correction in a sequential scenario.

526 correcting all data every time that a new rating sequence is processed, it would
 527 be corrected only the last p sequences of the most recent ratings in the dataset.
 528 This approach significantly limits the data to be processed in each iteration,
 529 considerably reducing the final running time and the intrusiveness of the original
 530 proposal since the number of instances identified as noise is reduced with a
 531 shorter time horizon.

532 Figure 3 illustrates this approach. Here, once the new rating sequence s_k is
 533 gathered, a temporal dataset T containing such a sequence, as well as previous
 534 ones. The natural noise management used as the starting point for these models
 535 (Section 2.4) is applied over this temporal dataset T , and at the last stage, the
 536 values of the modified ratings in T are updated in the original dataset R used
 537 for recommendation generation. Algorithm 2 screens this approach.

538 Overall, the computational cost of both approaches presented in this
 539 section depends on two main factors: 1) The cost of the classification-based
 540 approach for natural noise management, which is used at the initial step in
 541 both approaches, and 2) The cost of the inner approaches for rating

Algorithm 1: Pseudocode for the incremental time-aware natural noise management proposal. *seq* method.

Input : R_{data} the sorted set of ratings to be checked for natural noise detection and correction
 s_{list} a list of rating sequences, $s_1, s_2, s_3, \dots, s_k, \dots, s_n \in R_{data}$, continuously gathered by the recommender system
 $th1$ first classification thresholds
 $th2$ second classification thresholds
 δ difference threshold

Output: $R_{corrected}$ list of corrected ratings

SequentialNNCorrection(R_{data}, s_{list})

```

1  $R_{corrected} = \{ \}$ 
2 foreach new  $s_k$  do
3    $R_{temp} = R_{corrected} + s_k$ 
4    $R_{noise} = \text{identifyNoiseRatings}(R_{temp}, th1, th2)$ 
5   foreach  $r_{ui}$  in  $R_{noise}$  do
6      $R_{corrected} = \text{correctNoisyRating}(r_{ui}, R_{temp}, \delta)$ 
7   end foreach
8 end foreach
9 return  $R_{corrected}$ 

```

542 prediction. In the first case, considering that full inspection of the rating
543 matrix is necessary, the theoretical cost would be $O(|U| * |I|)$, where U and I
544 are the sets of users and items. However, due to the sparsity of RS datasets,
545 this matrix can be quickly inspected. In the second case, the complexity of the
546 different rating prediction methods varies from methods with constant time to
547 methods with higher complexity. Moreover, in the experimental section, it will
548 be proved that, in practice, the approach is able to correct several ratings in a
549 short period. In addition, it will be proved how the considered length of the
550 sequence can manage such execution time while maintaining positive values in
551 terms of accuracy for almost all the evaluated settings.

552 4. Experiments and results

553 This section executes an evaluation process to measure the impact of the
554 proposed alternatives to natural noise management in an incremental
555 time-aware recommendation scenario. We assume two main criteria for the

Figure 3: Overview on an improved approach for natural noise correction in a sequential scenario, considering the correction of the last k sequences.

556 performance evaluation: recommendation accuracy after the execution of the
 557 correction method in the data and the amount of rating modified by the
 558 correction process. With this aim, we initially discuss the experimental setup
 559 and then present and analyze the obtained experimental findings.

560 4.1. Evaluation protocol

561 In this study, we evaluated how our natural noise preprocessing approach
 562 increases data quality, thereby affecting recommendation accuracy. Therefore,
 563 we will compare the results provided by our sequential approach versus two
 564 different cases: the case of not applying natural noise methods and the case of
 565 applying the natural noise method identified as baseline (Yera et al., 2015), but
 566 without considering the sequential nature. After applying the selected natural
 567 noise method, the recommendation results were evaluated using a five-fold cross-
 568 validation approach.

569 It is important to highlight that the same rating prediction model is used
 570 for both the preprocessing natural noise step and the final recommendation.

Algorithm 2: Pseudocode for the incremental time-aware natural noise management proposal, considering the correction of the last k sequences. *seqk* method.

Input : R_{data} the sorted set of ratings to be checked for natural noise detection and correction
 s_{list} a list of rating sequences, $s_1, s_2, s_3, \dots, s_k, \dots, s_n \in R_{data}$, continuously gathered by the recommender system
 $th1$ first classification thresholds
 $th2$ second classification thresholds
 δ difference threshold

Output: $R_{corrected}$ list of corrected ratings

SequentialKNNCorrection()

```

1  $R_{corrected} = \{ \}$ 
2 foreach new  $s_k$  do
3    $R_{temp} = \cup_{i=k-p+1}^k s_k$ 
4    $R_{noise} = \text{identifyNoiseRatings}(R_{temp}, th1, th2)$ 
5   foreach  $r_{ui}$  in  $R_{noise}$  do
6      $R_{temp} = \text{correctNoisyRating}(r_{ui}, R_{temp}, \delta)$ 
7   end foreach
8   foreach rating  $p_{ui}$  in  $R_{temp}$  do
9     if rating for  $(u, i)$  not in  $R_{corrected}$  then
10       $\text{Add } p_{ui}$  to  $R_{corrected}$ 
11      if  $p_{ui} \neq r_{ui} \in R_{corrected}$  then
12         $r_{ui} = p_{ui}$ 
13      end foreach
14 end foreach
15 return  $R_{corrected}$ 

```

571 The next subsection further details the prediction models used to evaluate the
572 natural noise management schemes proposed here. For the sequential proposal,
573 it is necessary to simulate a real-world environment. Specifically, the initial
574 training dataset will comprise data for the first ten weeks of the time frame
575 linked to the dataset used in the experiments. The natural noise process is
576 then performed over the entire dataset, adding the next week's information in
577 a sequential manner.

578 4.2. Models

579 In order to obtain robust results and to serve as a comparative basis for
580 the state-of-the-art, all prediction models included in the Python Surprise

581 package (Hug, 2020) have been included in the experimentation. The selected
 582 models are included in Table 4. It is important to note that each model uses
 583 the default configuration set in Surprise.

584 The approaches proposed in this work, *SeqNNM* and *SeqNNM-p*, are
 585 identified for simplicity by *seq* and *seqk*, respectively, in the experimentation
 586 carried out.

Model	Reference
BaselineOnly	(Koren, 2010)
CoClustering	(George & Merugu, 2005)
KNNBaseline	(Koren, 2010)
KNNBasic	A basic collaborative filtering algorithm (Resnick et al., 1994).
KNNWithMeans	A basic collaborative filtering algorithm, taking into account the mean ratings of each user (Resnick et al., 1994).
NMF	(Luo et al., 2014)
NormalPredictor	Algorithm predicting a random rating based on the distribution of the training set, which is assumed to be normal.
SVD	(Salakhutdinov & Mnih, 2008)
SVD++	(Salakhutdinov & Mnih, 2008; Koren, 2008)
SlopeOne	(Lemire & Maclachlan, 2005)

Table 4: Recommendation algorithms used.

587 4.3. Datasets and evaluation metrics

588 Our evaluation protocol selects two different versions of the MovieLens
 589 dataset (Harper & Konstan, 2015), which is a popular one in the RS field and
 590 additionally has a timestamp for each rating. First, MovieLens100k contains
 591 100,000 movie ratings associated with 943 users, about 1682 items, where each
 592 rating belongs to the range [1, 5]. Second, the last 1 million instances of the
 593 MovieLens25M dataset, which contains 1,000,000 movie ratings associated
 594 with 8715 users, about 5667 items, where each rating is in the range [1, 5]. It
 595 is important to highlight that these datasets have been considered

596 state-of-the-art datasets in recommender systems and are currently used by
 597 several research works (Abdalla et al., 2023; Acharya et al., 2023; Latrech
 598 et al., 2023; Mohammadpour et al., 2023).

599 To evaluate the performance of the proposals, we perform a five-fold
 600 cross-validation approach, where 80% of the samples compose the training set
 601 and the remaining 20% the test set, and measure the recommendation
 602 accuracy through widely used metrics such as the Mean Absolute Error
 603 (MAE), the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), Normalized Discounted
 604 Cumulative Gain (NDCG) (Wang et al., 2013), Precision, Recall, and F1-Score
 605 (F1). The NDCG metric (Järvelin & Kekäläinen, 2002) relies on Discounted
 606 Cumulative Gain (DCG) and it is grounded in the assumption that highly
 607 relevant items appearing toward the end of a search result list should be
 608 penalized. This is because the graded relevance value diminishes
 609 logarithmically in proportion to the position of the result. The formalization
 610 of DCG is as follows:

$$DCG_u = \sum_{k=1}^N \frac{r_{u, recom_{u,k}}}{\log_2(k+1)} \quad (1)$$

611 where $recom_{u,k} \in I$ is the item recommended to user u in k position.

612 To calculate NDCG, the DCG value needs to be normalized by dividing
 613 it by the maximum achievable DCG value, known as $DCG_{perfect}$ (Järvelin &
 614 Kekäläinen, 2002). $DCG_{perfect}$ represents an ideal recommendation list where
 615 the most preferred items are ranked at the top. The NDCG values for each user
 616 are computed as follows:

$$NDCG = \frac{DCG}{DCG_{perfect}} \quad (2)$$

617 As a final step, the NDCG values associated with individual users are

Performance measure	Definition
MAE	$\frac{1}{ R_{test} } \sum_{r_{ui} \in R_{test}} p_{ui} - r_{ui} $
RMSE	$\sqrt{\frac{\sum_{r_{ui} \in R_{test}} (p_{ui} - r_{ui})^2}{ R_{test} }}$
Precision	$\frac{TP}{TP + FP}$
Recall	$\frac{TP}{TP + FN}$
F1-Score	$\frac{2 * Precision * Recall}{Precision + Recall} = \frac{2 * TP}{2 * TP + FP + FN}$

Table 5: Performance measures used for evaluating the recommendation accuracy.

618 averaged to derive the final reported NDCG value. Additionally, we extract
619 the number of modified values through the natural noise correction process
620 and the running time of the complete experimentation. The definition of the
621 most known performance measures used is included in Table 5.

622 The intrusiveness of the studied models is another important parameter to
623 be analyzed and is evaluated through the number of values modified by the
624 applied natural noise techniques. In this scenario, a greater number of modified
625 values indicates greater intrusiveness of the method.

626 Finally, the running time of each proposal is recorded to evaluate its
627 scalability.

628 4.4. Experimental results

629 In this section, we present the experimental findings for the specified
630 protocol. To facilitate the reading of this work, we have included a graphical
631 analysis of the most relevant performance metrics of the obtained results.
632 Furthermore, the tables with numerical results present all the metrics included
633 in Section 4.3 for the results associated with the models proposed in Section
634 4.2.

635 4.4.1. *MovieLens 100k dataset*

636 The results included in Table 6 show a robust improvement in the
637 recommendation performance when we apply traditional or sequenced natural
638 noise corrections. In the same way, for each recommendation method, the
639 proposed sequential natural noise correction process (*seq*) obtains the best
640 results in most cases. The BaselineOnly method combined with the proposed
641 sequential natural noise process obtained the best results in RMSE, MAE, and
642 Precision metrics. The KNNBasic method obtains the best results in Recall
643 and F1-score metrics, but these results are not very different from those
644 obtained by BaselineOnly. On the other hand, SVD++ obtained the best
645 results for NDCG. This metric is particularly relevant to this type of problem
646 and is gaining importance over time. SVD++ also offers very competitive
647 results in other metrics, especially RMSE, MAE, and Precision. BaselineOnly
648 obtains the best results at the cost of being the second most intrusive method
649 after NormalPredictor. It is important to note that methods that are
650 significantly less intrusive than BaselineOnly, such as SVD++ or KNNBasic,
651 are able to provide similar performances.

Table 6: Results obtained for MovieLens 100k dataset: no natural noise method (no), baseline natural noise proposal (nn), the sequential proposal (seq), and the sequential method considering the last k rating sequences (seqk). The best cases for each method are highlighted in blue. The best results are stressed in bold.

Models	Natural Noise Approach	RMSE	MAE	NDCG	Precision	Recall	F1	Modified Ratings	Running Time (secs)
BaselineOnly	no	0.94397	0.74837	0.91373	0.69851	0.54736	0.61375	0	5.42
BaselineOnly	nn	0.73562	0.56683	0.94282	0.74252	0.5931	0.65943	14527	82.9
BaselineOnly	seq	0.69145	0.52756	0.94781	0.74274	0.60026	0.66393	18801	823.75
BaselineOnly	seqk7	0.82979	0.63833	0.92695	0.71381	0.56736	0.6322	12639	22.04
BaselineOnly	seqk9	0.81738	0.62711	0.92944	0.71457	0.56816	0.63299	13636	26.07
BaselineOnly	seqk11	0.80611	0.61738	0.93161	0.7148	0.56906	0.63363	14538	29.55
CoClustering	no	0.96511	0.75564	0.91146	0.67569	0.52317	0.58971	0	14.39

CoClustering	nn	0.7839	0.59991	0.93614	0.71232	0.54387	0.61676	12128	95.89
CoClustering	seq	0.73695	0.55406	0.94128	0.70904	0.54747	0.61784	17336	930.93
CoClustering	seqk7	0.85769	0.65025	0.92227	0.69189	0.53694	0.60463	12639	36.38
CoClustering	seqk9	0.84457	0.63813	0.92599	0.6917	0.5391	0.60592	13636	40.77
CoClustering	seqk11	0.83104	0.62507	0.92859	0.69702	0.54175	0.60963	14538	44.17
KNNBaseline	no	0.93067	0.73321	0.91707	0.70963	0.55883	0.62525	0	23.46
KNNBaseline	nn	0.78182	0.61532	0.9342	0.72728	0.57847	0.64437	9118	109.05
KNNBaseline	seq	0.72807	0.5677	0.94141	0.73846	0.59383	0.65828	13288	961.72
KNNBaseline	seqk7	0.82601	0.63355	0.92688	0.71363	0.56972	0.63359	12639	41.68
KNNBaseline	seqk9	0.81297	0.62229	0.92989	0.7164	0.57407	0.63736	13636	45.64
KNNBaseline	seqk11	0.80226	0.6132	0.93147	0.71699	0.57367	0.63734	14538	48.93
KNNBasic	no	0.97973	0.77363	0.91803	0.71338	0.57295	0.63548	0	19.22
KNNBasic	nn	0.82952	0.64888	0.93443	0.73341	0.59483	0.65686	9727	104.4
KNNBasic	seq	0.77754	0.60621	0.94196	0.74138	0.61219	0.67062	14299	959.35
KNNBasic	seqk7	0.88091	0.67166	0.92788	0.72211	0.60014	0.65549	12639	37.49
KNNBasic	seqk9	0.86868	0.6612	0.93041	0.72	0.60349	0.65659	13636	43.01
KNNBasic	seqk11	0.85936	0.65272	0.9322	0.72193	0.60793	0.66002	14538	45.24
KNNWithMeans	no	0.95108	0.74946	0.91567	0.68056	0.51733	0.58781	0	19.98
KNNWithMeans	nn	0.80108	0.62861	0.93254	0.68745	0.52302	0.59405	9720	106.05
KNNWithMeans	seq	0.74683	0.57921	0.93856	0.69499	0.53312	0.60338	13959	955.23
KNNWithMeans	seqk7	0.84329	0.64594	0.92451	0.68255	0.53001	0.59667	12639	38.77
KNNWithMeans	seqk9	0.82989	0.63392	0.92739	0.68241	0.53205	0.59789	13636	42.87
KNNWithMeans	seqk11	0.81836	0.62373	0.92885	0.68343	0.53378	0.59939	14538	46.03
NMF	no	0.96249	0.75687	0.90787	0.68878	0.5195	0.59224	0	11.77
NMF	nn	0.7939	0.6144	0.92838	0.70282	0.53452	0.60721	11402	101.52
NMF	seq	0.71873	0.54495	0.94004	0.70567	0.54037	0.61205	18591	975.34
NMF	seqk7	0.85485	0.65374	0.91966	0.69491	0.52477	0.59796	12639	33.96
NMF	seqk9	0.84386	0.64306	0.92158	0.69736	0.52753	0.60067	13636	38.16
NMF	seqk11	0.83255	0.63226	0.92417	0.69742	0.52862	0.60138	14538	41.64
NormalPredictor	no	1.51801	1.21871	0.84491	0.56385	0.40898	0.47406	0	4.02
NormalPredictor	nn	1.35557	1.08223	0.86073	0.57832	0.42143	0.48754	15008	74.3
NormalPredictor	seq	1.14326	0.90008	0.89593	0.6135	0.435	0.50904	23706	822.8
NormalPredictor	seqk7	1.42868	1.14532	0.85411	0.56781	0.4173	0.48106	8841	21.26
NormalPredictor	seqk9	1.42409	1.14037	0.85299	0.56273	0.40565	0.4714	9607	25.42
NormalPredictor	seqk11	1.4159	1.13243	0.85334	0.56188	0.40983	0.47394	10119	28.88
SVD	no	0.93613	0.73759	0.91493	0.7011	0.54362	0.61239	0	10.28
SVD	nn	0.81262	0.64443	0.93194	0.72134	0.56343	0.63265	7529	78.55
SVD	seq	0.72243	0.56203	0.94186	0.72042	0.56841	0.63543	15187	826.52
SVD	seqk7	0.83305	0.63869	0.92487	0.70523	0.54711	0.61618	12639	24.79

SVD	seqk9	0.81917	0.6264	0.92756	0.70506	0.5509	0.61849	13636	29.1
SVD	seqk11	0.80833	0.61691	0.92952	0.70614	0.55291	0.62019	14538	32.23
SVD++	no	0.91996	0.72135	0.92007	0.70957	0.55054	0.61999	0	161.33
SVD++	nn	0.76528	0.59833	0.94018	0.73672	0.57562	0.64626	9516	278.67
SVD++	seq	0.69185	0.53127	0.94812	0.73353	0.57863	0.64692	16526	1626.78
SVD++	seqk7	0.8214	0.6287	0.92771	0.70928	0.54968	0.61935	12639	209.55
SVD++	seqk9	0.80695	0.6157	0.93113	0.71169	0.55375	0.62283	13636	225.11
SVD++	seqk11	0.79739	0.60744	0.93202	0.71164	0.55571	0.62406	14538	231.04
SlopeOne	no	0.94587	0.74335	0.91307	0.69392	0.5373	0.60563	0	17.9
SlopeOne	nn	0.75652	0.58208	0.93877	0.73282	0.56969	0.64102	12353	100.62
SlopeOne	seq	0.72831	0.5593	0.94202	0.73311	0.5726	0.64297	14467	945.27
SlopeOne	seqk7	0.83611	0.63703	0.92545	0.70573	0.54892	0.61751	12639	36.77
SlopeOne	seqk9	0.82315	0.62512	0.92824	0.70779	0.55154	0.61994	13636	40.56
SlopeOne	seqk11	0.81254	0.61553	0.93024	0.70708	0.54976	0.61855	14538	44.05

652 In order to facilitate the comparison between the *nn* model and the *seq*
653 model, Table 7 shows the percentage improvement obtained in each metric. In
654 this case, a considerable improvement can be seen in all performance metrics in
655 practically all cases. In the case of running time and the number of modified
656 values, we see how *seq* is more time-consuming and intrusive. Both metrics
657 show the cost of obtaining better results.

Table 7: Percentage of improvement (%) of the *seq* proposal vs. the state-of-the-art *nn* proposal for MovieLens 100k dataset.

Models	RMSE (%)	MAE (%)	NDCG (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1 (%)	Modified Ratings (%)	Running Time (secs) (%)
BaselineOnly	6.00446	6.92800	0.52926	0.02963	1.20722	0.68241	-29.42108	-893.61290
CoClustering	5.98928	7.64281	0.54906	-0.46047	0.66192	0.17511	-42.94195	-870.83685
KNNBaseline	6.87498	7.73906	0.77178	1.53723	2.65528	2.15870	-45.73371	-781.88837
KNNBasic	6.26627	6.57595	0.80584	1.08670	2.91848	2.09481	-47.00319	-818.95722
KNNWithMeans	6.77211	7.85861	0.64555	1.09681	1.93109	1.57057	-43.61111	-800.76381
NMF	9.46845	11.30371	1.25595	0.40551	1.09444	0.79709	-63.05034	-860.71504
NormalPredictor	15.66205	16.83099	4.08955	6.08314	3.21999	4.40989	-57.95576	-1007.35500
SVD	11.09867	12.78649	1.06445	-0.12754	0.88387	0.43942	-101.71337	-952.24599
SVD++	9.59518	11.20786	0.84452	-0.43300	0.52291	0.10213	-73.66541	-483.75989
SlopeOne	3.72892	3.91355	0.34620	0.03957	0.51080	0.30420	-17.11325	-839.40943

658 To analyze the results more clearly, some graphical comparisons have been
659 included.

Figure 4: RMSE results for the multiple models and natural noise approaches selected in the MovieLens 100k dataset.

660 Figure 4 includes the RMSE results for every model tested and all the
661 natural noise approaches included in this work. The comparison shows how
662 the application of any natural noise correction technique improves the final
663 results obtained using all the methods. Our first proposal, sequential and
664 cumulative natural noise correction (*seq*), provides the best results for all
665 models, with significant improvements over the traditional approach (*nn*). Our
666 second proposal (*seqk*) offers results that are progressively closer to those
667 obtained by the traditional method (*nn*) as the value of k increases. This
668 behavior is relevant in massive data or Big Data environments considering that
669 *seqk* works with a reduced subset of data while *nn* needs all available data.
670 Moreover, in the case of SVD, *seqk11* is able to provide better results than *nn*,
671 so in these environments, the *seqk* approach becomes a desirable alternative.

672 The NDCG metric (Table 7) shows a similar behavior to that observed for

673 RMSE. The *seq* approach obtains the best results, *nn* obtains the second
 674 place, followed by the different *seqk* approaches, the higher the *k*, the better
 675 the performance. This metric shows reduced differences between *seqk* and *nn*,
 676 and it is possible to improve the results of the traditional approach with slight
 677 increases in the *k* parameter. It is important to note the reduction of resources
 678 associated with the *seqk* approach, both in time and memory, by processing a
 679 subset of the original data at each step.

Figure 5: Running time (secs) results, in logarithmic scale, for the multiple models and natural noise approaches selected in the MovieLens 100k dataset.

680 Figure 5 shows the running time obtained from each approach. The
 681 difference between the *seq* approach with respect to the rest is quite clear.
 682 This approach requires the longest running time. In the second place, we
 683 found the traditional approach (*nn*), while our second proposal (*seqk*) offers a
 684 considerable reduction in the running time concerning *nn*. Since the cost in
 685 the result performance is reduced, the *seqk* approach provides a robust

686 alternative in environments where time is a constraint to be considered.

Figure 6: Number of modified ratings produced for each model and natural noise approach evaluated combination in the MovieLens 100k dataset.

687 Finally, Figure 6 shows the number of modified values for each model and
 688 approach. The *seq* approach is the most intrusive among the models, except
 689 for the SlopeOne and KNN-based models. The *seqk* approach is more intrusive
 690 as the value of k increases. This behavior shows that a higher data availability
 691 leads to higher natural noise detection and, therefore, higher intrusiveness. Re-
 692 evaluation of the data when new data are sequentially added also leads to greater
 693 intrusiveness, as in the *seq* case.

694 4.4.2. MovieLens last 1M of 25M rating dataset

695 In this section, experimentation close to a real use case in a data-intensive
 696 environment is performed, allowing us to evaluate the performance and
 697 scalability of the proposals.

698 The results shown in Table 8 show a clear dominance of the SVD++ model

699 with the proposed *seq* approach, obtaining the best results in terms of RMSE,
700 MAE, and NDCG metrics. BaselineOnly, also with the *seq* approach, obtains
701 the best Precision and F1-Score results. Finally, the KNNBasic model, with the
702 *seq* approach, obtains the best results in the Recall metric. Although the *seq*
703 approach is more data-intrusive than traditional approaches, the differences in
704 performance results are very significant, as can be seen in Figure 7.

Table 8: Results obtained for MovieLens 1M dataset: no natural noise method (no), baseline natural noise proposal (nn), the sequential proposal (seq), and the sequential method considering the last k rating sequences (seqk). The best cases for each method are highlighted in blue. The best results are stressed in bold.

Models	Natural Noise Approach	RMSE	MAE	NDCG	Precision	Recall	F1	Modified Ratings	Running Time (secs)
BaselineOnly	no	0.9045	0.71412	0.92298	0.71811	0.56994	0.63551	0	81.92
BaselineOnly	nn	0.7166	0.55467	0.94705	0.75102	0.6053	0.67033	128249	8719.99
BaselineOnly	seq	0.67968	0.52162	0.95098	0.75287	0.61615	0.67768	165506	217044.8
BaselineOnly	seqk7	0.80165	0.6189	0.93435	0.72684	0.58262	0.64679	119606	413.4
BaselineOnly	seqk9	0.79905	0.61663	0.93488	0.72732	0.58339	0.64745	121959	472.42
BaselineOnly	seqk11	0.79576	0.61395	0.93543	0.72697	0.5834	0.64732	124459	558.41
CoClustering	no	0.91263	0.71281	0.92464	0.7037	0.55873	0.62289	0	154.11
CoClustering	nn	0.74229	0.57018	0.94482	0.73056	0.58374	0.64895	112804	7666.49
CoClustering	seq	0.70363	0.53261	0.94903	0.72924	0.58704	0.65046	159584	216431.68
CoClustering	seqk7	0.81639	0.62191	0.93382	0.71153	0.56614	0.63056	119606	512.84
CoClustering	seqk9	0.81084	0.61768	0.93454	0.71241	0.56971	0.63312	121959	564.73
CoClustering	seqk11	0.80871	0.61482	0.93519	0.71262	0.56884	0.63266	124459	698.63
KNNBaseline	no	0.89624	0.70529	0.92375	0.71945	0.57261	0.63769	0	616.48
KNNBaseline	nn	0.80037	0.63473	0.93192	0.72558	0.58042	0.64493	55729	8346.76
KNNBaseline	seq	0.75403	0.59515	0.9372	0.72954	0.58999	0.65239	89148	220434.11
KNNBaseline	seqk7	0.79971	0.61733	0.9335	0.72539	0.58096	0.64518	119606	936.94
KNNBaseline	seqk9	0.79711	0.61523	0.9339	0.72647	0.582	0.64626	121959	987.28
KNNBaseline	seqk11	0.79384	0.6126	0.93454	0.72578	0.58225	0.64614	124459	1067.88
KNNBasic	no	0.93529	0.73738	0.92439	0.71818	0.5988	0.65308	0	747.07
KNNBasic	nn	0.83961	0.66558	0.93129	0.72443	0.60933	0.66191	57210	9396.34
KNNBasic	seq	0.79088	0.62373	0.93677	0.72915	0.61907	0.66962	97594	223299.58
KNNBasic	seqk7	0.84285	0.64746	0.93391	0.72832	0.61471	0.6667	119606	1078.19
KNNBasic	seqk9	0.84034	0.6453	0.93443	0.72934	0.61612	0.66797	121959	1167.65

KNNBasic	seqk11	0.8372	0.64272	0.93504	0.72881	0.61685	0.66817	124459	1285.16
KNNWithMeans	no	0.92434	0.73021	0.92135	0.68389	0.53334	0.59931	0	722.12
KNNWithMeans	nn	0.82265	0.65337	0.9305	0.68713	0.53587	0.60214	64782	8877.83
KNNWithMeans	seq	0.77313	0.60956	0.93567	0.68885	0.54257	0.60702	100863	220632.42
KNNWithMeans	seqk7	0.82257	0.63621	0.93127	0.69373	0.54538	0.61067	119606	899.73
KNNWithMeans	seqk9	0.81985	0.63386	0.93176	0.69437	0.54612	0.61138	121959	955.05
KNNWithMeans	seqk11	0.81645	0.63102	0.93243	0.6951	0.54673	0.61205	124459	1037.78
NMF	no	0.91588	0.7201	0.9193	0.69677	0.53433	0.60483	0	131.88
NMF	nn	0.74417	0.57726	0.94004	0.71794	0.55391	0.62535	114743	7632.58
NMF	seq	0.68188	0.5179	0.94891	0.71766	0.55887	0.62839	184003	215615.8
NMF	seqk7	0.81572	0.62808	0.92993	0.70578	0.53999	0.61185	119606	481.98
NMF	seqk9	0.81289	0.62539	0.93041	0.70684	0.54209	0.61359	121959	536.5
NMF	seqk11	0.80971	0.62283	0.93099	0.70592	0.54181	0.61307	124459	613.05
NormalPredictor	no	1.51028	1.21401	0.85059	0.55968	0.40268	0.46837	0	67.79
NormalPredictor	nn	1.35526	1.08332	0.86377	0.56656	0.40661	0.47344	141563	8376.64
NormalPredictor	seq	1.15084	0.90733	0.89786	0.60137	0.42608	0.49877	225176	219088.62
NormalPredictor	seqk7	1.42381	1.14078	0.85739	0.5567	0.40052	0.46587	83481	443.44
NormalPredictor	seqk9	1.42394	1.1409	0.85719	0.55744	0.40201	0.46713	84887	516.02
NormalPredictor	seqk11	1.42287	1.13982	0.85737	0.55785	0.40191	0.46721	87066	639.33
SVD	no	0.88207	0.69149	0.92781	0.72318	0.56249	0.6328	0	111.93
SVD	nn	0.76815	0.60688	0.94119	0.73858	0.57867	0.64892	67717	7982.44
SVD	seq	0.67975	0.52599	0.95112	0.73873	0.58529	0.65312	152278	215875.73
SVD	seqk7	0.79717	0.6131	0.93402	0.72525	0.56777	0.63692	119606	443.4
SVD	seqk9	0.79468	0.61109	0.93439	0.72634	0.56894	0.63808	121959	520.05
SVD	seqk11	0.79082	0.60806	0.93486	0.7249	0.56773	0.63676	124459	568.96
SVD++	no	0.86704	0.67483	0.93271	0.73233	0.57421	0.6437	0	3048.93
SVD++	nn	0.72654	0.5658	0.94897	0.7514	0.59207	0.66228	87500	11406.44
SVD++	seq	0.66065	0.50447	0.95588	0.74983	0.59762	0.66513	157357	250978.33
SVD++	seqk7	0.78568	0.60084	0.93794	0.73112	0.57334	0.64269	119606	3904.18
SVD++	seqk9	0.78296	0.59857	0.93867	0.73246	0.57374	0.64345	121959	3958.81
SVD++	seqk11	0.78011	0.5961	0.93889	0.73168	0.57429	0.6435	124459	4038.17
SlopeOne	no	0.90424	0.70993	0.92328	0.7088	0.55153	0.62035	0	285.17
SlopeOne	nn	0.72927	0.56432	0.94552	0.73887	0.57676	0.64783	114407	7821.6
SlopeOne	seq	0.70597	0.5449	0.94793	0.73975	0.58208	0.65151	134183	217920.66
SlopeOne	seqk7	0.80414	0.61754	0.93414	0.71629	0.55896	0.62792	119606	631.97
SlopeOne	seqk9	0.80164	0.61529	0.93465	0.71662	0.55938	0.62831	121959	681.4
SlopeOne	seqk11	0.79827	0.61249	0.93518	0.71641	0.55967	0.62841	124459	760.12

Figure 7: RMSE results for the multiple models and natural noise approaches selected in the MovieLens last 1M of 25M ratings dataset.

705 Additionally, Table 8 shows an increase in the running time for the *seq*
706 approach, while the *seqk* approach shows a significant reduction in the time
707 cost. Because each time window is seven days, the *seq* approach can be applied
708 in a real-world application without a problem. In the case of time constraints,
709 such as to prevent the use of the *seq* or *nn* approaches, the *seqk* approaches offer
710 competitive results (Figure 7), with respect to the traditional approach (*nn*).
711 Moreover, this approach allows us to improve its performance in terms of results
712 by adapting the time horizon k to the time constraints of each problem.

713 As in the previous case, the comparison between the *nn* model and the
714 *seq* model, by percentage of improvement, is included in Table 9. The results
715 show that a significant enhancement is evident across nearly all performance
716 metrics. When examining factors such as running time and the number of
717 modified values, it becomes clear that the *seq* approach is more time-consuming

718 and invasive. Both metrics highlight the trade-off involved in achieving improved
 719 results.

Table 9: Percentage of improvement (%) of the *seq* proposal vs. the state-of-the-art *nn* proposal for MovieLens 1M dataset.

Models	RMSE (%)	MAE (%)	NDCG (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1 (%)	Modified Ratings (%)	Running Time (secs) (%)
BaselineOnly	5.15211	5.95850	0.41497	0.24633	1.79250	1.09647	-29.05052	-2389.04875
CoClustering	5.20821	6.58915	0.44559	-0.18068	0.56532	0.23268	-41.47016	-2723.08614
KNNBaseline	5.78982	6.23572	0.56657	0.54577	1.64881	1.15671	-59.96698	-2540.95459
KNNBasic	5.80389	6.28775	0.58843	0.65155	1.59848	1.16481	-70.58906	-2276.45257
KNNWithMeans	6.01957	6.70524	0.55562	0.25032	1.25030	0.81044	-55.69603	-2385.20671
NMF	8.37040	10.28306	0.94358	-0.03900	0.89545	0.48613	-60.36098	-2724.94092
NormalPredictor	15.08345	16.24543	3.94665	6.14410	4.78837	5.35020	-59.06416	-2515.47151
SVD	11.50817	13.32883	1.05505	0.02031	1.14400	0.64723	-124.87411	-2604.38175
SVD++	9.06901	10.83952	0.72816	-0.20894	0.93739	0.43033	-79.83657	-2100.32074
SlopeOne	3.19498	3.44131	0.25489	0.11910	0.92239	0.56805	-17.28566	-2686.13991

720 Analyzing the results obtained by all models and approaches in both
 721 datasets, we can see that, except for the KNNBaseline model, the rest of the
 722 models obtain, in most cases, an improvement in the performance of the
 723 results. If we focus on the *seqk* approaches, we can appreciate that the
 724 performance differences for different values of k are more significant in the case
 725 of MovieLens100k than in MovieLens1M (Figures 4 and 7, respectively).
 726 These results show the importance of the temporal component in both
 727 scenarios, but it is more significant in small datasets. In addition, the
 728 importance of the parameter k can be appreciated, and it is advisable to adapt
 729 it to the type of problem addressed.

730 The results obtained for the *seq* approach, which are the best results in
 731 the vast majority of cases, require a large amount of running time (Figure 8).
 732 Because, in a real case, the accumulation of data takes weeks or even months,
 733 for the amount of data we are working on, the running time does not limit the
 734 application of our proposal in real scenarios. In the extreme case of working
 735 with large amounts of data and very tight model running time windows, we

736 always have the option of using the *seqk* approach. This approach allows us
 737 to adjust the performance and running time using the parameter k , which is
 738 especially useful for this type of problem.

Figure 8: Running time (secs) results, in logarithmic scale, for the multiple models and natural noise approaches selected in the MovieLens last 1M of 25M ratings dataset.

739 Finally, in Figure 9, we analyze the intrusivity levels of our MovieLens1M
 740 dataset and compare it with those obtained for the MovieLens100k dataset,
 741 Figure 6, we can appreciate a significant reduction of the relative intrusivity
 742 in each dataset. This behavior can be observed numerically by comparing the
 743 results included in Tables 6 and 8. This is especially relevant in the case of
 744 the KNN-based models, where the *seq* approach is the second least intrusive,
 745 marking a significant difference from the trend shown by the rest of the cases
 746 in both datasets.

Figure 9: Number of modified ratings produced for each model and natural noise approach evaluated combination in the MovieLens last 1M of 25M ratings dataset.

747 4.5. Discussion

748 The results obtained in the previous section show a considerable
 749 improvement in the data quality after the application of the two natural noise
 750 correction techniques proposed in this study.

751 The first approach proposed, *seq*, obtains considerable results improvement
 752 by adding and accumulating information sequentially (Tables 6 and 8).
 753 Although the intrusiveness is not high according to Figures 6 and 9, the
 754 computation required in high-dimensional problems may limit its use.

755 The second proposed approach, *seqk*, focused on the use of data related to
 756 the last k weeks, is able to provide competitive results in a short time at the
 757 cost of higher intrusiveness, considering the traditional natural noise approach
 758 (Figures 6 and 9) and a correct setting of the parameter k . This proposal
 759 uses a smaller amount of data, which allows its use in real problems with large
 760 dimensions and running time limitations (Figures 5 and 8).

761 Based on the obtained results, the application of natural noise correction
762 techniques has shown a robust increase in the quality of the processed data. For
763 this reason, its use is highly recommended in any RS problem. Furthermore,
764 with the development of the current work, it has been proved that applying
765 natural noise management approaches over small segments of rating data in RS
766 is feasible, which is a step-further viewpoint in relation to the former works in
767 natural noise management (Yera et al., 2015; Castro et al., 2017), which have
768 always used the whole dataset as input. According to our viewpoint, this is one
769 of the main contributions of this work in relation to previous contributions.

770 In addition, a well-defined balance was observed between the volume of
771 data used for training the natural noise management model and the degree of
772 accuracy improvement linked to such a trained model. Thus, a larger number
773 of rating segments used for training natural noise management leads to a
774 larger accuracy improvement. However, the use of a lower number of rating
775 sequences in the correction implies a more modest accuracy improvement.
776 Nevertheless, in this case, it is important to note that fewer sequences imply a
777 lower running time, which could be a variable that must be controlled in
778 practical application scenarios of the methods discussed.

779 The proposals presented in this paper improve the quality of the data
780 processed in recommender systems by incorporating temporal information of
781 interest into the natural noise-cleaning process in a transparent way for the
782 end user. This is because the two proposals can be applied to any
783 recommender system with temporal information since they can be included as
784 an additional step just before introducing the data into the final model.

785 An important shortcoming related to the approaches presented in the current
786 contribution is the lack of uncertainty management associated with the rating
787 data. The management of uncertainty has been previously proven to be a useful

788 component in natural noise management in recommender systems (Yera et al.,
789 2016, 2019). Future work will focus on this direction. In addition, future work
790 will explore different exponential functions for characterizing the importance of
791 each rating, according to their associated timestamp, for building user profiles
792 with the natural noise management-related task.

793 Furthermore, another important shortcoming of the current work is that it is
794 specifically focused on individual recommendations. However, previous studies
795 on natural noise management, such as (Castro et al., 2017), showed that this
796 task has a very positive effect on group recommender systems. Therefore, these
797 previous results highlight the necessity of exploring time-related natural noise
798 management, as screened in the current work, in group recommender systems
799 scenarios.

800 **5. Conclusions**

801 In recent years, several studies have shown that user preferences tend to be
802 inconsistent, which affects the accuracy performance of recommender systems
803 (RS). In order to address this issue, several preprocessing approaches have
804 been developed, processing these anomalous behaviors and obtaining a
805 positive impact on the recommendation precision.

806 In this study, we focus on the application of these preprocessing proposals
807 in real-time RS. To this end, we propose two incremental strategies to correct
808 noisy ratings in this scenario. Considering a simulated time-aware RS, we have
809 shown how these strategies are appropriate considering the recommendation
810 accuracy, running time, and intrusion level in the data. Specifically, it is
811 important to highlight that the achieved recommendation accuracy
812 outperforms the accuracy obtained by previous works on natural noise
813 management, such as those discussed in Section 2, and that the identified

814 intrusion degree is lower than the intrusion degree obtained by other data
815 preprocessing tasks in related data mining scenarios (Alexandropoulos et al.,
816 2019).

817 Beyond the theoretical and experimental results obtained across this paper,
818 the practical implications of the obtained results rely on the fact that they
819 illustrate that the time-related, sequence-driven management of natural noise
820 in recommender systems is feasible. While previous works in this area have
821 focused on performing this task over a large batch of data, the current work
822 illustrates that the noise correction of small data segments also leads to an
823 improvement in prediction accuracy and could provide additional benefits such
824 as smaller intrusiveness and a shorter running time. This natural noise
825 management over small data segments could be the key for generalizing these
826 types of approaches in currently deployed recommendation applications,
827 considering their huge amount of data that makes the use of previous methods
828 focused on the entire dataset inappropriate. This work holds potential
829 applications in domains characterized by the continuous generation of content,
830 which often experiences brief periods of trending. It requires proposals capable
831 of effectively integrating the temporal information and enhancing the data
832 quality for the final model. Examples of such domains include streaming
833 platforms and social networks, which frequently produce trending content
834 within specific timeframes.

835 In the next future work, the current proposals will be extended to the
836 group recommendation scenario (Castro et al., 2017). Furthermore, we will
837 focus on reformulating the current proposals using fuzzy tools (Castro et al.,
838 2018; Yera et al., 2019). As a major goal, we aim to minimize the number of
839 corrections required in past ratings and eventually work toward a framework
840 in which correction is performed just at the rating insertion moment. For this

841 purpose, we intend to exploit the sequential pattern mining theory (Mishra
842 et al., 2015) to model, at least partially, the inconsistencies that appear.

843 Additionally, we pretend to validate the current proposal through its use
844 for recommendation improvement in practical cases such as e-learning scenarios
845 (Yera & Martínez, 2017). Finally, explainable recommendations should also be
846 considered in this environment (Yera et al., 2022a).

847 **CRediT authorship contribution statement**

848 F.J. Baldán: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation,
849 Visualization, Software, Writing - Original Draft, Validation.

850 R. Yera: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing - Original Draft,
851 Validation.

852 L. Martínez: Writing – review & editing, Validation.

853 **Declaration of Competing Interest**

854 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or
855 personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported
856 in this paper.

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1150 69, 1109–1121.

1151 **Appendix A**

Algorithm A.1: Method to identify possible noisy ratings

Input : R_{data} the sorted set of ratings to be checked for natural noise detection
 r_{ui} current rating
 $th1$ first classification thresholds
 $th2$ second classification thresholds

Output: R_{noise} list of ratings identified as noise
identifyNoiseRatings($R_{data}, th1, th2$)

```
1  $R_{noise} = \{ \}$ 
2  $U = \{ \text{users providing ratings in } R_{data} \}$ 
3  $I = \{ \text{items rated in } R_{data} \}$ 
4 ClassifyUsers( $U$ )
5 ClassifyItems( $I$ )
6 foreach  $r_{ui}$  in  $R_{data}$  do
7   if  $u$  is critical and  $i$  is weakly-preferred and  $r_{ui} \geq th1$  then
8     |  $R_{noise} = R_{noise} + r_{ui}$ 
9   if  $u$  is average and  $i$  is averagely-preferred and ( $r_{ui} < th1$  or  $r_{ui}$ 
10    |  $\geq th2$ ) then
11     |  $R_{noise} = R_{noise} + r_{ui}$ 
12   if  $u$  is benevolent and  $i$  is strongly-preferred and  $r_{ui} < th2$  then
13     |  $R_{noise} = R_{noise} + r_{ui}$ 
14 end foreach
15 return  $R_{noise}$ 
```

Algorithm A.2: The rating correction approach

Input : R_{data} the sorted set of ratings to be checked for natural noise detection
 r_{ui} current rating to correct
 δ difference threshold

Output: r_{ui} rating corrected
correctNoisyRating(r_{ui}, R_{data}, δ)

```
1  $n_{ui} = \text{predict}(u, i, R)$ 
2 if  $\text{abs}(r_{ui} - n_{ui}) > \delta$  then
3   |  $r_{ui} = n_{ui}$ 
```
